

Accounting in commercialization departments of higher educational institutions

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Annotation

The Commercialization Department is a center engaged in the commercialization (i.e., marketing) of scientific and innovative developments in higher education institutions. The main function of the department is to identify, evaluate, protect and commercially implement scientifically important, but economically useful developments created at the university.

The role of the Commercialization Department in higher education institutions is to implement scientific and economic integration between higher education institutions and society. Accounting in the Commercialization Department is a system for ensuring, recording, analyzing and reporting on the financial flow of scientific and innovative projects (for example, patents, licenses, grants). Therefore, the accounting department plays an important role in demonstrating the effectiveness of the scientific activities and potential of higher education institutions.

Key words: *commercialization, patents and inventions, income and expenses, taxes and fees, analytical and synthetic accounting, double-entry bookkeeping.*

The Commercialization Department is a center engaged in the commercialization (i.e., marketing) of scientific and innovative developments in higher education institutions. The main function of the department is to identify, evaluate, protect and commercially implement scientifically important, but economically exploitable developments created at the university.

The Commercialization Department in Uzbek universities harmonizes the interests of society, the state and the higher education institution. The activities of the departments are strengthened by legislation within the framework of the reforms being implemented in the republic in the field of intellectual property protection, grants and patents.

The activities of the Commercialization Unit are carried out in accordance with the current legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regulatory legal acts and orders of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, other state administration bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the

field of intellectual property protection, the Charter of the Higher Education Institution, orders and decrees of the rector, internal procedures of the Higher Education Institution, the Regulation "On the Unit for Commercialization of Scientific and Innovative Developments of the Higher Education Institution" and other regulatory legal acts of the Higher Education Institution.

The role of the commercialization department in universities is to implement scientific and economic integration between universities and society, namely:

- the department is a mechanism connecting scientific research at the university and the industrial/market sector. It can be seen as a "bridge";
- in most universities, the commercialization department is directly subordinate to the rectorate or the innovation development department and is of strategic importance;
- it is a key factor in strengthening the university brand, generating income using grants and patents from the scientific potential base, and linking scientific forces to economic development.

The main areas of activity of the commercialization department are:

- systematic market analysis and demand for innovative products (works, services), assessment of the payback period associated with the commercialization of innovative products, study of profitability and risks;
- selection of promising projects with high commercial potential and ready for implementation;
- attraction of investors, partners and other interested parties for the implementation of innovative projects;
- cooperation with industrial enterprises in order to introduce new technologies and develop innovative products.

Accounting in the commercialization department is a system of insurance, accounting, analysis and reporting of financial flows of scientific and innovative projects (for example, patents, licenses, grants). In this case, the subject of accounting is the financial activities of the department and the cooperation of related persons (researcher, lawyer, investor); the object is patents, technology transfer, intellectual assets, costs and income associated with them. Theoretically, it is considered as a complete model of accounting turnover.

Accounting in the commercialization department performs the following tasks:

- organizes and maintains accounting in the department in order to provide interested external and internal users with complete and reliable information about the financial and economic activities and financial condition of the department;

- forms an accounting policy in accordance with regulatory documents on accounting, based on the characteristics of the business conditions, structure, level of relevance to the industry and other possibilities of the department's activities, which provides the opportunity to obtain timely information for assessing, analyzing, planning and controlling the financial condition and results of the department's activities;

- prepares and approves the forms of internal accounting reports, forms of primary accounting documents used to formalize business transactions, and an accounting work plan consisting of statistical and analytical accounts;

- ensures the procedure for conducting an inventory and property valuation, maintaining documents on the availability of property, its condition and value;

- organizes an internal control system for the correctness of formalizing business transactions in compliance with the document flow procedure;

- forms an accounting and reporting information system that ensures the provision of the necessary accounting information to external and internal users, meeting the requirements of accounting, tax, statistical and management accounting;

- carries out work on maintaining accounting registers using modern information technologies, progressive forms and methods of accounting and control;

- carries out work on accounting for the financial results of the department's activities, financial, accounting and credit operations, financial funds, material and production reserves, fixed assets, liabilities and property.

The accounting department of the commercialization department ensures:

- accurate and timely reflection of business transactions, movement of funds, formation of income and expenses and fulfillment of obligations in accounting accounts;

- timely transfer of taxes and fees to the republican, regional and local budgets, insurance contributions to state extra-budgetary social funds, payments to credit organizations, financing objects, funds to close debt on loans;

- control over the organization's spending of the payroll fund and the accuracy of employee payroll calculations, inventory, the procedure for maintaining accounting and reporting, and conducting statutory audits;

- participation in the organization's internal audit in conducting financial analysis and forming tax policy based on information from accounting and reporting;

- develop proposals aimed at improving the results of the financial activities of the department, eliminating financial losses and non-production expenses;

- ensure compliance with financial and treasury regulations, carry out work to ensure the legality of the exclusion of deficits, receivables and other losses from

accounting reports.

In this case, work is organized on the basis of accounting principles.

For example, 1. The principle of double entry: each financial transaction is recorded in the debit and credit directions. This principle is the basis for the reconciliation of the balance sheet and the arithmetic accuracy of financial statements. In the commercialization department, this actively works for each case related to property and obligations.

2. Reporting principles: the values applied in departmental accounting: consistency, prudence, objectivity, the primacy of substance over form. These principles are important for the consistency, optimization, compliance with investment conditions and intellectual property of credit and debit entries.

3. The principle of full accounting of costs: any costs are included in the cost, that is, they must be assessed on the basis of full accounting, regardless of material, labor, overhead costs (rent, utilities, administrative and marketing expenses) and non-commercial work.

The costs of scientific research and its commercialization include all costs that are directly related to these activities or that can be reasonably attributed to these types of activities.

The following expenses are included in the costs of scientific research and their commercialization:

- expenses for salaries and other payments to employees engaged in this activity;
- the cost of materials and services used in scientific research and their commercialization;
- depreciation of fixed assets during the use of assets;
- additional expenses directly related to this activity;
- amortization of patents and licenses and other similar expenses.
- expenses for sales costs.

Synthetic and analytical accounting in the commercialization department is carried out in harmony with each other and is organized as follows:

- Synthetic accounting is a general structure for accounting blocks (for example, income, expenses for commercialized projects). They are maintained in the form of a General Journal and a balance sheet.

- Analytical accounting is designed to conduct synthetic accounts in more detail, separately by indicators such as project, counterparty, date.

The processes of commercialization of scientific ideas are characterized as a

complex flexible system. In this case, accounting plays the role of the “data center” of this system, and any economic decisions made are linked to financial results. Strengthening the planning and financial analysis system is an important direction in this situation.

For the accountant of the commercialization department, intellectual property — not only an asset, but also patent costs, grant reports and distribution of income — becomes an accounting object. This means that the accounting department plays an important role in demonstrating the effectiveness of the scientific activities and potential of the higher education institution.

References:

1. National Accounting Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 11 “On approval of expenses for research and development”
2. National Accounting Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 7 “On Approval of Intangible Assets”.
3. National Accounting Standard of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1 “Accounting Policies and Financial Reporting”.
4. International Standard Financial Statements (MSFO/IAS) IAS38 "Intangible Assets".
5. Abdusalomova N.B. Accounting I-II-III parts. (Textbook). Tashkent, 2021.
6. Нечепуренко Ю.В. Коммерциализация результатов научно-технической деятельности. Минск, 2012.
7. Кузнецов Н.В., Миняев А.С. Особенности введения бухгалтерского учета деятельности малых инновационных предприятий, созданных при участии ВУЗов. //Современные проблемы науки и образования. <https://science-education.ru/article/view?id=13562>